

PARAMETERS AFFECTING MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE MANUFACTURED BY LIQUID RESIN INFUSION (LRI)

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SUMMARY

The mechanical properties of composite materials vary according to the manufacturing process and the constituents used. To understand the relationship between process parameters and mechanical properties of composites made by LRI, an experimental plan was designed. This study presents the results of statistical analysis of the influence of texture reinforcement, the process temperatures and configuration on the ultimate tensile and compressive strengths of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy RTM 6 laminates.

Keywords: LRI, process parameters, experimental plan, statistical analysis, UTS, UCS.

INTRODUCTION

The Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI) is one kind of closed mould process for manufacturing fiber-reinforced polymer structures. The resin infuses the preform reinforcement under vacuum through the thickness of the fiber fabrics. The LRI is classified [1] as a Vacuum Infusion Process (VIP). This process is considered as a low cost composite manufacturing process as it doesn't require additional pressure to compact the perform and inject the resin, and the resin curing is done out of autoclave. The vacuum bag (or flexible film) is used as upper mould. The use of the vacuum bag gives this process a relatively low process tooling cost to manufacture large composite structures for high-performance applications, in comparison to other processes using rigid moulds. The high porous media (HPM) layers is the distribution resin fabric which has a higher permeability than the perform reinforcement. It allows the resin to flow on the surface followed by through thickness flowing. This flow of resin results only from vacuum and gravity effects. The flow speed of the resin depends on the pressure gradient achieved in the cavity vacuum and also on the number of HPM layers used. In addition to the preform reinforcement texture, on which the mechanical properties, the resin infusion process also creates a variation in these properties. Thus, it is necessary to identify the process parameters and quantify their effects on the quality of composites for better control of manufacturing and to minimize the variation in properties.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the impact of the number of reinforcement layers, number of high porous media layers, the mould, injection and curing temperatures, and the side where the preform reinforcement is placed in the bottom mould, on the properties of carbon-epoxy RTM 6 laminates manufactured by LRI. To achieve this, the design of an experimental plan helped to manufacture these laminates under different

conditions, according to the values of process parameters. The goal of this work is to understand and determine the process parameters that have significant influence on the variation of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and the ultimate compressive strength (UCS) of laminates. The statistical analysis is used to quantify the effects of these parameters on the properties responses. A summary of the results will be made for a holistic view of the plan and to determine the best manufacturing conditions for optimum properties of composites.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Materials

The reinforcements used were two combinations of unidirectional (UD) carbon fiber fabrics called Non-Crimp-Fabric (NCF). They have the same properties (areal weight: 1088 g/m², type and rate of powder binder) and they are identical in architecture except for their stacking configuration. They are fabrics of carbon stacked quadriaxial to $-45^{\circ}/0^{\circ}/+45^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ and $+45^{\circ}/0^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$. These carbon NCF constitute the preform reinforcement in the LRI composites manufacturing. The choice of these two different stack-fabrics was made for the laying-up, to respect the mirror symmetry according to the orientation of the reinforcements inside the composite. They are commercial grade fabrics and supplied by SAERTEX [2].

The resin was a monocomponent thermoset resin HexFlow[®] RTM 6. It is a premixed epoxy system for service temperatures from -60°C up to 180°C (-75°F up to 350°F). Detailed information pertaining to this resin can be found elsewhere [3].

Process parameters and experimental plan

Research has been done to identify the key process parameters for the Vacuum Infusion Process (VIP) [1]. For the LRI process, a variant of the VIP, we detect some parameters which have a greater impact on the performance and the quality of a manufactured composite structure. We grouped these process parameters into three sets.

The *texture reinforcement* refers to the powder binder through the layers of fiber fabrics, the architecture of the preform such as weaving, knitting, stitching or z-pinning, and the number of stacked fabrics. The rate or type of powder binder through the layers of fiber fabrics contributes to the quality of the material [4]. This powder affects the properties of the composite [4, 5, 6, 7]. Stitching of preform has a fundamental impact on quality and mechanical properties of the composite, both during the manufacturing process through flow of the resin and during resin curing [5, 8, 9, 10, 11]. For this research, impact of stitching as a parameter on the performance of LRI composites will be the long term aim of future studies. In the current study, the type of reinforcement used already contains a defined type and rate of powder binder. This parameter is not included as a parameter in the analysis. Govignon [9] has shown by the Carman-Kozeny equation that the number of layers of fabric affects the fiber volume fraction of composite through thickness of the structure. This is an important parameter because this may have consequences either independently or by *interaction between* other

parameters (*HPM: High Porous Media for example*), on mechanical properties of the manufactured composite structure. These effects are more significant on tensile properties [6, 12]. In this study, set 1, "*texture reinforcement*" is only the *number of NCF layers*. It has two levels of variation. The preform may contain two or four NCF layers layed-up according to figure 1 below. The final laminate thicknesses was respectively approximately 2mm and 4mm.

Figure 1: Laying-up of the NCF layers according to the mirror symmetry

The second set is the *process configuration*. Several authors specify level of vacuum achieved during the resin injection in Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) process as a crucial parameter for obtaining a better quality of composite materials [4, 5, 7, 9, 13]. The manipulations carried out on the LRI process allowed us to understand that achieving a good vacuum level depends on the sealing obtained in the vacuum cavity (sheet of vacuum bag and bottom mold) during the manufacture. This value, which is the absolute pressure in the cavity, cannot be imposed. It varies according to knowledge of the assembly. For this reason, the "vacuum level" in this study is not variable and is not a parameter to be studied. Furthermore, the resin injection location, number of resin inlet point and/or type of resin injection gate (center, peripheric point or line for example), is a factor of composite properties variation [14]. Pearce [15] specifies its influence on velocity of resin for the filling in the mould cavity. This resin injection

location is confirmed as having effects on the fiber volume fraction and the void content of composites. In this study, number of resin inlet points and type of resin injection gates are constant. We use one line as resin inlet and another one for vacuum outlet. However, the two sides where preforms are located on the mould will be analyzed. The figure 2 shows a structure placed near the resin inlet and another one placed at the vacuum side. Parameter studied is "*vacuum side or injection side*". It is used to quantify influence of the position of specimens according to mechanical properties of the structure.

Figure 2: Experimental setup of LRI process

"*High porous media (HPM)*" is also identified in this set as an influencing parameter. It is a characteristic parameter for the flow of resin during the structure manufacture by VIP [16]. It could have influence on properties of composites either independently or *in interaction between the number of fiber layers* [12]. Identification of this parameter as impact factor is recent. Its consideration in analysis will allow us to better control its effects. We use for manufacturing LRI composite structures, 1 or 2 HPM, according to the process condition used.

The temperatures used during manufacturing process also generate variability of morphological and mechanical properties of final composites. The *process temperature* is the set 3. This is the *mould or preform temperature, resin injection temperature and resin curing temperature*. These temperatures have influence on the viscosity of the resin, thus on its flow velocity through the preform [4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 13]. These parameters are included in the study by varying their values in the ranges of temperature properties of the components. The use of these different values of temperature helps to discern their influence.

The seven process parameters found contributed to design and implementation of an experimental plan. The method used is table of Taguchi L8 [5]. Table 1 summarizes the experimental plan studied. It consists of seven columns of factors, process parameters, and eight lines representing different process conditions. Each factor has two levels of variation in the table. This plan is allowed to manufacture the NCF carbon/epoxy RTM6 composites under several experimental conditions.

Table 1: Description of experimental plan

		Process parameters						
N°	Exp.	Number of NCF layers	Number of HPM layers	Vacuum side or Injection side	Interaction NCF and HPM	Mould Temp. (°C)	Injection Temp. (°C)	Curing Temp. (°C)
1	5A	2	2	Vacuum	1	100	80	180
2	5I	2	2	Injection	1	100	80	180
3	6A	2	1	Vacuum	2	120	80	160
4	6I	2	1	Injection	2	120	80	160
5	7A	4	1	Vacuum	1	100	60	160
6	7I	4	1	Injection	1	100	60	160
7	8A	4	2	Vacuum	2	120	60	180
8	8I	4	2	Injection	2	120	60	180

Manufacturing of LRI composites

The figure 2 illustrates the experimental setup of LRI process. The manufacturing of composite structures is done in four steps: stacking of NCF which forms the preform reinforcement, laying-up of material elements on the tooling fabrication, injection and curing of resin, followed by cooling. Preforms are in two parts of 400 x 150 mm each, placed on a bottom aluminum mould of 500 x 500 mm. A release agent is applied on surface of the bottom mould to facilitate removing of the composite after cooling. Sealant tape is applied around the preform. The sheet of peel ply is placed above the preform to facilitate the removing of the upper part. HPM (1 or 2) is placed on the peel ply. A vacuum bag covers all of them. Vacuum is thus created in the vacuum cavity by the vacuum pump which is contained in the injection device (Figure 3).

The preform is heated at mould temperature (100°C or 120°C) on the heating table. Three thermocouples are placed at different locations to verify actual temperature during the process. Resin is then heated in the resin pot, degassed under vacuum, and injected in vacuum cavity to infuse the perform at injection temperature (60°C or 80°C). Injection continues until the resin exits the cavity by resin outlet. The same vacuum level is maintained till end of manufacturing. The composite manufacturing finishes with resin curing at curing temperature (160°C or 180°C) and cooling at ambient temperature (around 20°C). Table 2 shows the curing cycle laminates made according to their curing temperature. Two composite plates NCF carbon/epoxy RTM 6 were manufactured per experiment.

Table 2: Curing cycle of NCF Carbon/Epoxy RTM 6 composite plates

Curing temp. (°C)	Rise time (min)	Hold time (min)	Down time (min)
160	45	75	120
180	60	60	120

Figure 3: Device manufacturing LRI composites NCF Carbon/Epoxy RTM 6

Testing of properties

Three specimens were cut from each composite plate manufactured and tested in tension and compression. Tensile specimens of dimensions 150 x 20 x 2 or 4 mm are tested according to standard NF ISO EN 527-4 and compressive specimens (110 x 25 x 2 or 4mm) in accordance to standard Pr EN 285 Celanese [17]. The aluminum end tabs of 50 x 20 x 2 mm and 51 x 25 x 2 mm respectively were locally bonded to each specimen. The results of each tests were analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Statistical analysis

The aim of the analysis of results is to identify the potential impact of process parameters listed in experimental plan on the properties. These include, influence of process parameters on the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and ultimate compressive strength (UCS). Table 3 shows mean responses of the tests under several experimental conditions.

A multilinear regressive analysis is performed, combined with statistical tests. It allows the determination of the best model of the plan. The program data processing takes into account the method of algorithms optimization. It is the estimation of statistical regressive quantities, testing adequacy of the model and the effect factors [5]. For the decision of the best model, the probability of error is fixed equal to 5% ($\alpha = 5\%$). The parameter (factor) is considered to have significant (S) effects on the result (response), when for the analysis of variance, its probability (of having an effect equal to zero) is

less or equal to 5% ($\alpha \leq 5\%$). If $\alpha < 1\%$, the parameter is considered to be very significant (VS). This is low significant (LS) when the probability is between 5% and 10% and not significant (NS) in the other cases. The analysis is to find the model which contains only the parameters whose effects are statistically significant.

Table 3: Experimental design and outline of mean results

Experiments		Process parameters							Properties responses	
N°	Exp.	Number of NCF layers	Number of HPM layers	Vacuum side or Injection side	Interaction NCF and HPM	Mould Temp. (°C)	Injection Temp. (°C)	Curing Temp. (°C)	UTS (MPa)	UCS (MPa)
1	5A	2	2	Vacuum	1	100	80	180	689	485
2	5 I	2	2	Injection	1	100	80	180	701	402
3	6A	2	1	Vacuum	2	120	80	160	673	529
4	6 I	2	1	Injection	2	120	80	160	694	478
5	7A	4	1	Vacuum	1	100	60	160	751	511
6	7 I	4	1	Injection	1	100	60	160	772	524
7	8A	4	2	Vacuum	2	120	60	180	632	494
8	8 I	4	2	Injection	2	120	60	180	675	433

Effects on the ultimate tensile strength

The results of statistical analysis allowed us to identify the best model associated with the Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS). Mould temperature and curing temperature are the process parameters that have an effect on the UTS variation. The analysis of variance gives probabilities $\alpha_{T_{mould}}$ equal to 0.00036712 and $\alpha_{T_{curing}}$ equal to 0.00274769. The effects of mould temperature and curing temperature are marked very significant (VS) on the variation of UTS (α is less than 1%).

Figure 4 shows the effects of the variation of these two process parameters on the mean of UTS according to value of the temperature taken. UTS of composites NCF Carbon/Epoxy RTM 6 decreases by 60 MPa (for about 729 MPa to 669 MPa) with increasing of mould temperature from 100°C to 120°C. The same property of laminates cured at 160°C is found to be higher than those cured at 180°C. Its decreasing is about 48 MPa i.e. it varies from 723 MPa to 675MPa.

Figure 4: Effects of mould temperature and curing temperature on the ultimate tensile strength

Effects on the ultimate compressive strength

For analysis of the effects of process parameters on the Ultimate Compressive Strength (UCS), the best model refers to *curing temperature* as the parameter that most affects the variation of UCS. The UCS of composites NCF carbon/Epoxy RTM6 decreases by 50 MPa with an increase of curing temperature from 160°C to 180°C (Figure 5). "Vacuum side or injection side", which are the sides where composite plates were placed during the injection process, have a small influence in the results analysis. The probability of variance of this factor is 9.15% ($5% < \alpha < 10%$). However, it causes a variation of UCS of 7% down from the mean value of UCS in the plan. The decrease of UCS by 36 MPa occurs then by transition from vacuum side (mean value about 508 MPa) to injection side (mean value about 472 MPa).

Figure 5: Effects of curing temperature and side of composite plate on the ultimate compressive strength

Summary results

The purpose of this summary is to identify in a comprehensive manner, specimen composites which have the best properties to determine the better manufacturing conditions for structures loaded in tension and compression. Results of analysis show influence of process temperatures with exception of injection temperature on tensile and compressive properties. Figure 6 presents mean of ultimate tensile and compression strength of all experiments. UTS of composites NCF carbon/Epoxy RTM6 is better when they are manufactured at a lower mould and curing temperatures. UCS of composites is better when they are produced at lower curing temperatures and is also better when they were placed at the vacuum side during the injection procedure.

According to the analysis, other process parameters such as number of NCF layers, number of high porous media, or interaction of these two parameters have no effect on the characteristics of LRI composites in tension and compression.

Figure 6: Comparison between experiments and summary results in tensile and compressive test

CONCLUSION

The process parameters have been identified to allow design of experimental plan for manufacturing composites NCF carbon/epoxy RTM 6 by Liquid Resin infusion (LRI). Influence of these parameters on the ultimate tensile and compressive strength have been presented. The results of statistical analysis show the variation of ultimate tensile and compressive strength (UTS and UCS) significantly depends on increase of the process temperatures. So, UTS decreases with increase of mould and curing temperatures. The values of UCS of laminates decrease with increase of curing temperature. Besides, this last property is higher when structure is placed at the vacuum side instead of the injection side, during the production. The best manufacturing conditions for these types of loads are to use the low process temperature. In continuation of this work, other mechanical properties of these LRI composites such as

Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS) and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) are being studied. The integrity of composite material structures is also done using analysis of the fiber volume fraction, the void content, the thickness and the microstructure. The medium-term objective is the study of transverse reinforcement by stitching or Z-pinning of LRI composite structural parts and the impact of process parameters on these transverse reinforcements and the mechanical properties.

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